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A CRAM ON ESCALATION AND SCENARIO OF EMU FARMS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Emu Bird is a very tough bird with majestic appearance due to its height and look covered with brown feather coat. Emu farmers make the farming viable depending on the emu product sale like meat, feather, skin, oil which have demands in specific markets designed. More so the farming community tries to produce Emu chicks through hatching of eggs and sale the birds in pairs after due management and get good realization of value. Now when we consider the commercial viability of Emu farming by selling products it has been reported oil contribute significantly along with skin and Emu meat in the demanded market. But when we consider the cost of production of meat alone it looks expensive due to high FCR thus it demand superior price per kg of meat. Again to introduce any tender meat of Emu for higher price it would lose other sale values on paired grower stock sale, oil, skin etc., due to age effect. Thus this bird could not so far gain the required position for selling tender meat say by 20wk of age which become unviable. When we intend to derive all commercial products like oil, skin, feather etc., from the bird then only it justify the economical viability or commercial project viability subject to regular demand of products with reference to quality of such processed marketable products (oil, skin, meat, feather etc.). There need to be more processing infrastructures to make these Emu products attractive and gain market values which perhaps may come up in the Emu propagating locations through joint venture activities to support Emu farmers for economical values.

Processing activities for skin, oil, feather and also for meat (if desired) is now highly essential for boosting such commercial projects. Systematic collections of raw outputs like emu fat, feather, skin etc., are needed and also link with such processing units, so that quality of each commercial output can be preserved for developing final valuable products for consumers as expected. Such chain linkages are not visible widely with better technology so as to translate in to attractive ventures. Emu meat processing has also to be planned along with collection of other outputs so that the meat can be marketed gradually in the demanded markets. There are reports available that some restaurants are now serving Emu meat preparations and getting popular but to locate volume of the market we need to have processing technology involved in Emu sector. Other possibilities of common platforms for Emu propagation for commercial viability would be to support regular production and marketing introducing integration programs which may attract investors in this sector.

Key Words: Emu chicks, hypo-allergenic oil, EMU farming, Golden bird, Biosecurity measures

Introduction

In India, chicken is the most popular of the poultry species Followed by ducks & quails. Of late, with some popularization through Newspaper write ups, television coverage & Exhibitions, about 250-300 Progressive farmers of Maharashtra state have started Emu farming with 25 to 200 pairs in Pune, Thane, Nasik, Akola, Ahmed Nagar, Beed, Kolhapur districts and many more are coming up for guidance and Inquiring about the availability of bank loan for establishment of a new farm or expansion of existing farms. At present more than 10,000 pairs of Emu reared by the farmers in the state. For large scale production of meat oil and skin there is a long term potential for breeding and rearing of more than 75000 Emus. To promote such innovative project activity in the state this can accelerate capital formation in the rural area. NABARD, MRO, Pune has taken a decision to formulate a Model project for rearing of Emu as there is an increasing demand for such unit in coming Years.

The emu is a member of the ratite family, as are ostriches, rheas, kiwi and cassowary. An Emu's characteristics are small wings and a breastbone with no keel. They are generally originated from all continents south of the equator, except for Antarctic. Emu's do not get as big as an ostrich. They grow to about 5 - 6 feet tall from their head. They are very gentle birds and some are friendly, depending on how they are raised. However, they do have sharp claws that could really hurt a person if you try to catch one that is not friendly or sick.

Some farmers use emus for their meat, the meat is very lean and has a taste similar to beef. The emu's oil is a highly penetrating, hypo-allergenic oil with cosmetic and medical applications. The Emu is the second largest bird in the world and is very docile. They enjoy the companionship of people and can be curious, playful and friendly. Emu's can have their own personalities.

Statement Of The Problem

In general it seems that the Emu farming has tremendous hidden values which need marketing strategies. The other part of the species is that "this bird can be an ideal pet" which can find place in any farm house just like other pets and birds. In the recent past Emu farmers could suddenly realized the direct marketing of Emu products are getting harder although the financial institutions could consider these farming projects considering the possibilities of market values. But it seems there is decline in one state and picking up in other state which is natural as all farming community expects good returns from their investment, labor and time. Emu Farmers in India should take necessary initiatives to sell Emu meat oil in local markets to get out of the crisis and also farmers must do look for markets for Emu oil locally. Refining of the Emu oil by associating themselves by the farmers is need of the hour.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To study about the origin of EMU farms.
2. To know about EMU products and its applications.
3. To study the business plan and income level from EMU farming.
4. To analyze the current marketing scenario of EMU farming.

Origin Of Emu Farms

Recognizing the economic importance, Australian Government in 1975 Started domesticating these birds living in Jungles by establishing big farms. This Activity spread to America. France and other European countries in the early eighties. It is reported that there are about 90,000 Emu farms in America and an Emu Association was established in 1993. The activity has also spread to China, Japan, Malaysia and Korea.

One Emu farm by name Vijaya Ratite Farm (Pvt.) Ltd. was established by Shri P. Satyanarayana in Andhra Pradesh in 1996 on small scale. Similarly in Maharashtra state Shri.Ganesh Kale& Group introduced 20 pairs of Emu during 2001 & in Baramati Shri. Sandip Taware has established first Emu Farm with 10 pairs in April 2002. He has also established Emu hatchery. At present there is Four Emu Association in India. One is at Hyderabad name of "INDIAN EMU ASSOCIATION" Mumbai "NATIONAL EMU ASSOCIATION" headed by Shri. Sami Tambatkar. This two association working all India level. And in Maharashtra level at Baramati in the name of "Maha Emu Association" headed by Shri. Sandip Taware and another at Pune in the name "Emu Farmer Association" headed by Mrs. Chitralekha Mehta. The experience of the farmer has been encouraging.

The Emu is a native of Australia and was originally imported to the United States from 1930-1950 as exotic zoo stock. The average adult weights between 110 and 140 pounds. Their height is about 5-1/2 feet tall. The female emu can lay eggs for about 20 years. She begins to lay about the age of two or three years. The female emu can lay 20-50 eggs per year. Their eggs are edible and taste like chicken eggs if scrambled. The emu's life span is supposed to be about 25-35 years. Emus can generally adapt to most climates and may be raised anywhere in the U.S. Emu's should have some type of shelter for cold winters and shade for summer. Emu's are generally pretty hardy, can develop intestine worms. It is a good practice to give Emu "Ivomec" or similar several times a year. It can be bought in a paste form. There are other preventatives that can be bought in a powder form to put in their water. Generally Emu's can be put with livestock with no problem.

Wal-Mart firm sells EMU materials. The emu farming business in southern Africa is viable. Emu is an expensive bird to grow. There is no money to be made raising emus for meat, only for breeding stock. Endorsed by popular film personalities, it expanded business to Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Kerala. Mr. Guru even opened a chain of restaurants in Bangalore, New Delhi, Pondicherry and Erode, among other places, inviting State and Central Ministers and famous personalities for inaugurations.

Development Of Emu Farms

Current Industry Status

The new entrants purchase chicks wherever available and rear them to the age of 2 to 3 years on their farms, the males and females are reared together, when they approach maturity and are ready to breed, they are counted and sexes approximately set in equal numbers, the Emu females select their mates to form breeding pairs and begin to mate, eggs come approximately 6 to 8 weeks after the first mating is seen, eggs are collected in the evenings, during the breeding season that begins from September/October and continues through march, collected eggs are washed and cleaned and sent for artificial incubation and hatched, the chicks that hatch are reared for 2 to 3 months and sold to new entrepreneur's or retained by those who want to expand their existing facilities. This way Emu chicks and growers have moved from Andhra Pradesh to Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Maharashtra and several other states.

The farm average egg production from a pair does not exceeded 20 eggs per season , many get less than 15 eggs average from a pair, this is because of inbreeding depression of egg production, breeding of poor breeders and no genetic improvement work being done. Farmers make several mistakes as a result of poor knowledge, rumors a misinformation that causes egg damage due to washing, cleaning, and poor storage, lower hatch abilities, poor brooding causing chick mortality and disabilities, there is no system of weighing and monitoring the eggs during incubation.

Many farmers feed a variety of leaves and vegetables to save on the commercial feed that is costly, no one makes his own feed, feed is purchased from commercial feed manufacturing units that make poultry feed and use their poultry knowledge and information for the Emu's these feed millers have no Emu experience or many have never seen an Emu in their life and they advise feed restriction as one with poultry breeders for better performance. Lot of wrong/false information circulate the Emu industry, with respect to the breeder performance, meat and oil yields, skin and feathers, hatching eggs and chicks, grower birds and adults.Emu is known as a Golden bird of the livestock industry, 98% of the bird's body is usable, practically no wastage. The Indian Emu industry since its beginning is a breeder chick market, every chick produced has been sold as a breeder to new entrepreneurs this trend will continue 3-5 more years, till it reaches the saturation point, when a large number of birds will have to be pushed into the meat market simultaneously yielding oil, skin and feathers.

Presently the farmers have numerous problem in the management, nutrition, disease control, egg production incubation, chicks survival and growth areas these problem will reduce with time, experience and adaptation of modern technology. Once the Emu birds are made available continuously to the meat processing industry, meat from slaughtered birds, fat rendering and oil processing, tanning of skins and their marketing will ensure economic viability and quick development of the Emu Industry.

Legal Status

Emu an exotic bird in India, not included in any schedule of the wildlife act 1972. The provisions of the wildlife protection Act 1972 and rules / amendments make there under are not applicable for the Emu birds. Therefore no permission is required from the Forest Department anywhere in the country.

Technical Parameters Of Emu Bird

The birds reach their full size by the end of 1st year. They grow up to 5.5 to 6 feet with a weight of 40 to 70 KGS. Laying period in India starts after 18 to 24 months and

Eggs are laid during September to February. Eggs are dark bluish green in color with a weight of 450 to 700 gms. A bird can lay 20-60 eggs in a season. Incubation period is 50- 52 days and newly hatched bird will be of 6-7”in height. The life span of the bird is 30-35 years. The productive economic life of the bird is 20.25 years.

Economic Importance (Scope)

It is reported that the price of Rs.18, 000/- a pair of 3 months old Birds and the price of Rs.40, 000/- a pair of 15 months old Birds having live body weight each 40 to 50 kg and the birds are used for table purpose.

Meat:

Meat of Emu bird is reddish in color, soft and with less of cholesterol 98% fat free. Emu meat is lower in fat than Chicken, Turkey, Pork & Beef It is the “Super Food of the New Millennium”. The price commands higher price than that of meat from other birds/animal and is reported at Rs. 300-450 per Kg. The American Heart Association has included Emu meat in its listing of heart healthy meats. Emu are higher in protein, vitamin c and iron compared to beef; lower in cholesterol compared to chicken. Emu gives red meat lovers what they want and health conscious consumers what they need. In fact, the American heart association recognizes emu meat as a healthy alternative to beef.

TABLE 1 SHOWING COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON EMU FARMS WITH OTHER ANIMAL FARMS.

NUTRITION/ TYPES	EMU	CHICKEN	LEAN PORK	LAMB
Fats (g)	2.4	3.5	25.0	23.4gr
Protein (%)	20.9	20.1	20.2	16.6
Energy (ki)	446.5	125.0	147.0	-----
Calories	106.2	125.0	147	282.0
Iron(mg)	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.55
Cholesterol (mg)	51.7	80.0	65.0	73

TABLE 2 SHOWING COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON EMU FARMS WITH OTHER ANIMAL FARMS.

NUTRITION/ TYPES	EMU	CATFISH	CHICKEN	BEEF
PROTEIN	23.3G	18.2G	23.1G	19.9G
CALORIES	109	113	110	225
CHOLESTROL	57.5MG	58MG	64MG	65MG
FAT	1.7G	4.3G	1.2G	15.8G
SATURATED FAT	0.06G	1.0G	0.3G	6.5G
MONO-UNSATURATED FAT	0.7G	1.6G	0.3G	7.2G
PLOY-UNSATURATED FAT	0.4G	1.0G	0.3G	0.6G

Feathers:

Feathers are soft non allergic / anti static, beautiful double quelled and are used In hats, dresses, computer and car cleaning brushes and household decorative items. About 400 to 600 Gms of feathers would be available from a bird and each bird would fetch about Rs. 200/- at present.

Skin:

The skin is very thin, soft and strong. Price of good quality skin is reported Rs.700/- to Rs.1000/- per Sq ft. and 8-12 sq.ft of skin is available from a well matured bird. The skin is used in the preparations of shoes, bags, belts, purses, jerkins and seat covers for expensive cars. At present raw skin of a matured bird would fetch about Rs. 1000 to 1200/-.

Egg shells and nails:

The egg shells are used for painting and as decorative items due to deep Blue Color. Nails are strong and decor able used in artificial ornaments and craft goods.

Oil:

About 4-6 a litter of oil is available from a bird which is devoid of any color taste and odor. At present market prices, the price of one litter refined Emu oil is Rs. 3000/- to Rs. 4000/- The oil is penetrating and is having moisturizing. Analgesic, ant allergic and antiseptic properties. The oil is used in analgesic ointments, beauty creams and lotions, soaps, hair oils, shampoos, perfumes and massage oils. The raw fat/crude oil of Emu fetches Rs.1000 per Kg. Traditionally Emu oil has been used for treatment of muscle and joint pains. Clinical experience with Emu oil has shown that it's two major benefits are its anti- inflammatory properties and its ability to penetrate the skin. It also appears to provide some solar protection.

Research and development of Emu oil using in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals is rapidly expanding. Emu oil has been documented to exhibit the following properties and/or has been used for the following purposes.

- Anti - Inflammatory Activity

- Moisturizing
- Cholesterol Reducer
- Bacteriostatic
- Penetration Enhancer
- Significant epidermal proliferative activity
- Non – Comedogenic
- Significant wound healing agent
- Significantly reduces recent keloid scarring
- Appears to promote faster healing of burns with less pain and scarring
- Anti - Arthritic Activity
- Excellent Emulsifier

EYES: The bird is able to see up to a distance of 10 meters and its eyes are being used to replace damages corneas in human beings.

UTILITY: 15 months old Emu broiler weighing 40 Kg. slaughtered for oil, meat and skin etc. The utility is as under:-

Utility	Present market price of produce per unit
43% boneless meat	Rs. 300/- to Rs. 450/ Kg.
14% bone meat	Rs. 200/ Kg.
5% feather & skin	Rs. 200 + Rs. 1000
22% fat	Rs. 1000 / Kg (raw oil)
3% leg skin	Rs. 500/-
4% neck	Usable but not saleable at present.
3% blood	Usable but not saleable at present.
4% waste	Usable but not saleable at present.
About 96% useable bird Refined oil	Rs. 3000/- to Rs. 4000/- Per Liter.

What type of shelter/fence does an emu need?

Fences should be tall enough to prevent the emus from escaping over the top. If an emu gets spooked for some odd reason, they will attempt to jump the fence. The minimum height should be about 6 foot. Use fencing that is safe so the emu won't get his/her head stuck or tear its feathers or hide. Fencing such as chain link or cattle link can be used. If using china link, sure to use double knuckled wire. The emu could cut their neck and die using the type that is barbed. Place the fence post on the outside of the fence. Emu's generally walk the fence line. This is normal behavior for emus. Emu's require some type of shade. They should also have a some type of shelter, even if it is only three sided. However, emu's can withstand pretty cold temperatures. But, if the temperature reaches 10 or less, it would be a good idea to walk them into their house.

The most important factors in the incubation hatching period are:

1. Temperature
2. Humidity
3. Fresh Air Flow
4. Egg Rotation
5. Rotation

The following are the most commonly used indicators:

Room Temperature	70-80°F
Incubation Temperature	96-98°F
Hatcher Temperature	97-98°F
Relative Humidity	25-60%
Wet Bulb Temperature	72-85°F
Incubation Period	47-53 days

(It will be necessary to make adjustments as your climate dictates).

The first one or two eggs which are laid each year may prove to be infertile or may be smaller than normal. If eggs in the incubator are not developing and become rotten; they will have an offensive odor. A rotten egg can explode and contaminate the incubator. If the egg is found that is sweating, remove it. An infertile egg may go full term without having a visual effect. The infertile egg will feel loose and slush at some point during incubation. While handling the eggs every three to four days, situation to be noticed. Open the incubator once a day to check for odors.

Few Facts About Our Favorite Emu

Height at birth	8 - 10 inches
Adult Height	5 - 6 feet tall
Adult weight	100 - 140 pounds
Colour	Black and Brown
Health	Generally Robust, Hardy
Temperament	Friendly, Docile
Lifespan	35 to 40 years (approx)
Productive years	Up to 25 years
Eggs per year	Average egg laying 10 to 15 eggs in the first breeding season, gradually increases up to 20-30 eggs in subsequent breeding seasons
Age at slaughter	16 – 18 months
Incubation Period	48 - 52 days
Percentage of eggs hatched	Approximately 70 percent
Space per Adult Bird	600 sq.ft. red and hardy soil

Health Issues In Emus

- **EMU CHICKS:** An emu chick with a navel that has not drawn in properly is susceptible to contaminations of the yolk sac or an infected navel. Check the newborn chick often and check for smelly fluids leaking from the navel. If this is present, this is a sign of infection. The emu chick will then require antibiotics or surgery to save the chick. Even if there is no fluids leaking from the navel, a lethargic, run down chick may be experiencing yolk sac problems. If the chick don't pass a dark green stool within five days after hatching is not using the yolk sac and will probably further problems resulting in death if no treated. If after five to seven days your chick makes no effort to eat or drink and has a large swollen stomach that feels hard to touch, there is reason to believe that the yolk sac is

not being utilized properly or may possibly be infected. The chick will probably not grow at a normal weight and will seem slow and lethargic as the problem manifest itself.

- **ADULT EMUS:** If an emu is discovered laying down more than a few days, it should be checked for illness or injury. An emu that walks around with its head hung low and eyes closed most of the time is cause for a concern. Possible causes could be: Impaction or internal or external injury.
- **IMPACTION:** If the emu makes several attempts to defecate with no success and its tail or rump seems to remain up in the air, this sign could be impaction. Tube feeding with Metamucil or Mineral oil could bring relief to the emu. Emus have been known to swallow wire, nails or sticks that have gotten hung up in the guy and do not ever pass. If this is the case, the emu will probably go off its feed and eventually go down or possibly continue to eat but, lose weight.

Mushrooming Of Emu Firms

The success of Mr. Guru's business model led to the mushrooming of emu firms, which advertised heavily in the Tamil media. Some even promised a return of Rs. 2 lakh a month for an investment of Rs. 10 lakh. Obvious to the fact that there are no processing facilities for products derived from emus, the investors bought these firms' claims that they exported emu meat and that everything from an emu was marketable. Many firms reportedly even engaged in trading of birds among themselves instead of marketing the emu meat, oil and skin (for leather). Sensing that something was wrong, the Erode district administration issued repeated warnings asking people not to fall for the tempting offers from these firms.

SALEM: Thousands of farmers, lured by private firms, have been queuing up to invest in emu farms in Salem and Erode in the hope of making a quick buck, investing life savings or borrowing money to start a business. But the first signs of a bubble burst were evident at a grievance redressal meeting held in the city on Friday, when farmers complained they were suffering losses and were being cheated. For the first time, the Salem district administration stepped in to advise farmers not to invest in the emu business.

Fall Of Emu Farms In Tamilnadu

Perundurai, the hub of emu farms, is now crowded with anguished investors who swallowed the bait of big returns. A conservative estimate by district officials points to a scam worth Rs. 300 Crore. But traders in the poultry business claim over Rs. 500 Crore might have been lost in this business. The police have said Susi Emu Farms India Private Limited might have swindled investors of around Rs. 200 Crore; most of these are from Tamil Nadu.

Promised staggering financial returns, more than 20,000 people invested in these firms. In 2006, M.S. Guru, hailing from Perundurai, founded Susi Emu Farms and introduced a buy-back scheme that promised lucrative returns on investment in contract emu farming. For an initial investment of Rs. 1.5 lakhs, he promised a return of Rs. 3.34 lakhs within two years. Under the scheme, the company provided investors three pairs of chicks on the payment of Rs. 1.5 lakhs as caution deposit. It also provided the infrastructure to rear the birds and offered Rs. 6,000 a month for the maintenance of the birds, besides a yearly bonus of Rs. 20,000. Thus, the investor was offered around Rs. 1.44 lakhs. As per the scheme, the company would take back the birds after two years and return the deposit too. When word got out that Susi Emu Farms made prompt payments, the investments poured in; in no time the company's presence spread all over Tamil Nadu.

Soon after, the firm introduced a VIP scheme, taking advantage of the lack of awareness among people about the birds. Under this scheme, the investor had to deposit Rs. 1.5 lakhs. But unlike the regular scheme, the firms promised to rear the chicks and pay the investors Rs. 7,000 a month and an annual bonus. For the first time, the Salem district administration stepped in to advise farmers not to invest in the emu business. But traders in the poultry business claim over Rs. 500 Crore might have been lost in this business.

The Bubble Bursts

The bubble burst when Susi Emu Farms failed to pay the monthly maintenance fee to the investors. After waiting for some time, the investors made a beeline for the firm's office in Perundurai. On August 6, Mr. Guru and his entire family disappeared. Others in the business followed suit, abandoning scores of investors and the birds. The police have registered cases against Mr. Guru and seven others under Section 120-B (conspiracy)

and 420 (cheating) of the Indian Penal Code and formed three teams to nab the culprits. About 4,000 investors from across the State have registered their complaints against these firms so far, the police said. This is not the first time Mr. Guru has been caught in a controversy. Earlier, he was arrested for misusing the former President, A.P.J. Abdul Kalam's name in promotional material.

Recommendations possible:

- Emu farming in India can safely continue and new ventures are to be planned by investors for infrastructures on processing back up.
- Integration can be tried only when systematic approach is identified and planned for market .However in all such activities cost and benefit ratios are basic deciding factors for which investors have to come up.
- Feed cost can be reduced for this large bird during growing and maintenance period by introducing fodder and other cheap vegetables as part feeding practices. If needed all these vegetable items could be processed for easy digestibility and creating attraction for the bird at low cost.
- The families of good status who have very fond of animals and birds need to be supplied Emu bird for their farm house only in pairs as these birds can live up to 10-15years easily at any place of India and would add to the beauty of the campus and keep happy all humankind and create good bonding. This trend would create huge market demand in India the way people have bonding with good size dogs, horse etc.
- Zoo sector and teaching sectors will have all time demands round the year on regular basis if the bird is available.
- The size of Emu farming need to be decided as per the market availability in the area and good standard husbandry practices would lead to new path of progress in times to come.

Conclusion

Emu farming offers great scope & potential because of its supplementary income, additional employment & simplicity in operation .Efficient emu development can be Achieved by promotion of small units in villages through a gamut of functions like Dissemination of information & technology, making various inputs & organizing training Sessions for farmers on this subject. After going through the forgoing paragraphs it is concluded that the captioned proposal is found to be technically feasible and financially viable.

Biosecurity measures to be taken in Emu Farming / breeding as suggested by Commissioner of Animal Husbandry, Maharashtra State are followed.

- ✚ The farm should be ideally placed and away from the population and is biosecured.
- ✚ The housing should be proper will adequate brooding facilities.
- ✚ There should be a separate workers team, who should not be allowed to get mixed with other workers.
- ✚ There should be separate dress code for the workers.
- ✚ Proper dis-infection procedures / foot dips etc., should be maintained.
- ✚ The quarantine sheds should be separate and away from other sheds.
- ✚ The other birds (parent, commercial or pure line etc.) and pets should not be reared/allowed to enter the same farm.
- ✚ The brooding space should be optimum.
- ✚ There should be provision of showers, change over and dips.
- ✚ Proper records should be maintained.
- ✚ There should be scientific facility for disposing off / destroying the bedding / dead Birds etc.
- ✚ The equipment is proper, properly disinfected and separate.
- ✚ The farm should have a water sanitation system.
- ✚ Water source should be tested for mineral, bacterial, chemical, contamination and pathogen load.
- ✚ Proper storage of feed to prevent contamination should be made. The water quality should be checked periodically and if contamination is seen it should be treated with any sanitizer.
- ✚ Routine disease monitoring procedures like postmortem examination of dead birds and periodic sera antibody assay is recommended.

Thus, the only way for emu farming to survive in India is to rely on the international export markets. This is a very difficult task to accomplish, and can only be achieved with the help of skilled technical consultants who have a thorough knowledge of the international market rules and regulations related to emu products. It is the right time for emu farms in India to improve and stand up to the global expectations and make a name for them in the international market.

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